

**SCHOOL HEADS ROLE AS CORRELATE TO POSITIVE
TEACHERS IDENTITY IN SELECTED SCHOOL
IN HINABANGAN SY 2023**

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School Heads Role as Correlate to Positive Teachers Identity in Selected School in Hinabangan SY 2023

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Abstract

The purpose of the study entitled “School Heads’ Role as Correlate to Positive Teachers’ Identity” in Selected School in Hinabangan SY 2023 is to determine the role of school heads in building positive teacher’s identity in the field of teaching. Based on the findings of the study, the school heads themselves indicate their Supervision and monitoring (Feedback), instructional support, and teacher’s Empowerment were practiced to a very high extent as assessed by themselves and the teachers. The teachers indicated their school heads’ role in supervision and feedback to a very great extent, particularly in observation in classrooms, Supervision and monitoring of the work and behavior of teachers, and creating an orderly atmosphere in the school. In the Teachers’ Empowerment role of the school head, teacher-rated their school head to practice these roles to a very great extent, particularly in advising teachers to enhance their professional development, Inform teachers about possibilities for updating their knowledge and skills, and giving them teachers the freedom to choose their own instructional techniques. Viewing school heads’ leadership through the lens of those at the school level provides direction for school improvement efforts by illuminating the successes and barriers that teachers face as they strive to work beyond the classroom. This study is recommended to widen the level of understanding of this component of school reform at all levels. A further study on this concept is recommended.

Keywords: *school heads role, teacher’s identity, public school teachers*

Introduction

School heads/Principals of the twenty-first century are charged with leading instruction as never before. Schools are failing at consistently delivering quality differentiated, researched based instruction. In order to lead a campus that delivers top quality instruction, principals need to recruit, develop and retain good teachers. In interviews with teacher candidates, it is easy to see the enthusiasm and eagerness they have for wanting to begin their careers; teaching, forming positive relationships with students and preparing them for the future. However, as teachers leave teacher training programs and enter the profession, there is often a disconnectedness between the training they receive and the realities of their first teaching assignment. First year teachers are expected to perform the same job duties as veteran teachers but often perform them with less skill and ability because they are new to the profession.

One of the most consistent findings from studies of effective school leadership is that authority to lead need not be located in the person of the leader but can be dispersed within the school between and among people. There is a growing understanding that leadership is embedded in various organizational contexts within school communities, not centrally vested in a person or an office. The real challenge facing most schools is no longer how to improve but, more importantly, how to sustain improvement. Sustainability will depend upon the school’s internal capacity to maintain and support developmental work and sustaining improvement requires the leadership capability of the many rather than the few. (Bill Mulford. 2013)

Who are teacher leaders? They are experienced and respected role models, who are innovative, organized, collaborative, trustworthy, and confident facilitators of learning. They model integrity, have strong interpersonal and communication skills, display the highest level of professionalism, a commitment to teachers and students, and expertise, and demonstrate a passion for learning, while taking the initiative as influential change agents (Danielson, 2006). Teacher leaders use data and other evidence in making decisions, recognize opportunities and take the initiative, mobilize people around a common purpose, identify resources and take action, monitor progress and adjust the approach as conditions change, sustain the commitment of others, and contribute to a learning organization (Danielson, 2006). Teacher leaders may be district appointed staff who fulfill specified roles of leadership, like instructional coaches, or they may be confident teachers who naturally assume or are asked to lead their grade level or department team members.

In the study entitled “Defining Teacher Leadership: Affirming the Teacher Leader Model Standards” by Cosenza, Michael N. 2015. Although there is no common definition for teacher leadership, the concept is continually advanced as a key component for both the success of schools and the professionalization of teachers (Boles & Troen, 1994; Dozier, 2007; Greenlee, 2007). Teachers need to be given opportunities to leave the isolation of their classrooms to collaborate with others in order to build leadership capacity (Dozier, 2007). The development of teacher leadership is increasingly viewed as an important factor in improving schools, improving student achievement, and retaining teachers for the long term (Dozier, 2007; Greenlee, 2007). Many educators and educational researchers have put forward standards and guidelines for teacher leadership. The most recent contribution to this initiative is a set of teacher leader standards developed by the Teacher Leadership Exploratory Consortium in 2011 which are the basis for this study. The consortium that developed the teacher leader model standards did so with the intention to provide guidance about teacher leadership and to delineate for universities and other providers of professional development a set of guidelines for the preparation of future teacher leaders (Teacher

Leader Model Standards, 2011). The standards have recently been adopted by two teacher leadership certificate programs in southern California. This study seeks to discover how teachers define the term teacher leadership and then compare those findings to the seven domains of the teacher leader model standards. Further, it aims to discover if these standards are in alignment with the viewpoints of practicing teachers.

The purpose of this study is to determine the role of the school heads in building the level of positive teacher’s identity and the essentialities associated with teacher leaders, focus on student learning, empowerment, relationships, and collaboration. Further, it aims to determine the level of school heads, particularly on the supervision and feedback, instructional support, teacher’s empowerment, and mentoring and coaching.

Research Questions

The purpose of this study is to determine the role of school heads in building positive teacher’s identity in the field of teaching. Specifically, this study aims to answer the following questions:

1. What is the assessment of the teachers and school heads themselves on the Role of School Heads in terms of:
 - 1.1. supervision and feedback;
 - 1.2. instructional support; and
 - 1.3. teacher’s empowerment?
2. What is the assessment of the teachers and the school heads themselves relative to teachers’ identity in terms of:
 - 2.1. professional competence;
 - 2.2. mastery of the subjects; and
 - 2.3. Relationship with peers?
3. Is there a significant difference on the assessment of the teachers and school heads themselves on the Role of School Heads in terms of:
 - 3.1. supervision and feedback;
 - 3.2. instructional support; and
 - 3.3. teacher’s empowerment?
4. Is there a significant difference on the assessment of the teachers and the school heads themselves relative to building teachers identity in terms of:
 - 4.1. professional competence;
 - 4.2. mastery of the subjects; and
 - 4.3. relationship with peers?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the role of school heads and positive teacher’s identity:
 - 5.1. role of the principal;
 - 5.2. building teachers’ identity?

Methodology

Research Design

A descriptive research design was used in this study. Simultaneously, in concurrence with the descriptive research design, quantitative research method was applied. Quantification of data using the aid of descriptive and inferential statistics will be apply to compute for the results and analysis of data.

Quantitative descriptive research aims to explain the characteristics involving samples and populations and is highly dependent on numerical data and statistical analysis. It can answer what, when, where, when and how questions, but not why questions, while the Descriptive study describes the variables that occur naturally between and among them.

Respondents

The researcher applied the total enumeration as the population. One hundred teachers from 10 selected Elementary school in the first district of Hinabangan Samar Year 2022-2023 and ten school heads and it serves as the respondents of the study as presented in the table.

Table 1.

	<i>Teachers</i>			<i>School Head</i>			<i>No. Of Respondents</i>
	<i>M</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Total</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Total</i>	<i>Total</i>
School 1	1	9	10	1	0	1	11
School 2	1	9	10	0	1	1	11
School 3	2	8	10	0	1	1	11
School 4	3	7	10	0	1	1	11
School 5	2	8	10	0	1	1	11
School 6	1	9	10	1	0	1	11

School 7	1	9	10	1	0	1	11
School 8	2	8	10	1	0	1	11
School 9	1	9	10	1	0	1	11
School 10	2	8	10	1	0	1	11
Total	16	84	100	6	4	10	110

Instrument

The study made use of a researcher-made structured research instrument. Since this is research made test, validation of the instruments conducted Test-retest method will be used. A gap analysis was done to determine some of the teachers' aspirations on the development of their identity by their school head, also reading from different books, unpublished study give ideas on the development /construction of the instrument.

Part 1 on the questionnaire is the role of school heads, particularly on: Supervision and Feedback; Instructional Support; and Teacher's Empowerment. It has three items per category. The survey instrument used a 5-point Likert scale to measure the extent of the variables being measured.

The extent does school heads built the positive teacher's identity in terms of professional competence; mastery of the subjects; relationship with peers, growth and development. The survey instrument used a 5-point Likert scale to measure the extent of the variables being measured.

Procedure

In gathering data, the researcher first secure letter of permission and endorsement from the researcher adviser on the conduct of the study and forwarding the letters to the District Office for approval. The approved letter was presented to the school head for their confirmation and approval for the conduct of the study in the school.

Letter for the teachers was also prepared and arrangement with them for the distribution of the instrument.

The main respondent of this study were the teachers, their observation, experiences, and perception toward the role of their school head. While the school heads were the subject of the study.

Data Analysis

For SOP 1 and 2 weighted mean was used to determine the assessment of the teachers and the school head themselves, weighted mean was use.

SOP 3 & 4 the t-test was used determine the significant difference in the assessment of the two groups on the role of the school heads in terms of: supervision and Feedback, instructional Support; and Teacher's Empowerment

The the t-test formula is is used in this study determine the significant difference between the means of two different groups.

In the interpretation and analysis on the result of study p-value was used with the following interpretation:

If the p-value is small (< 0.05), it indicates a piece of strong evidence against the null hypothesis. As a result, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Thus for a hypothesis with a p-value less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. This means that the results of the research/ study are statistically significant.

If the p-value is large (> 0.05), it indicates weak evidence against the null hypothesis. As a result, the null hypothesis is not rejected.

SOP 5, the Pearson correlation coefficient was used to determine the relationship of the two variables used the role of school heads the positive teacher's identity.

Ethical Considerations

The goals of research often include understanding real-life phenomena, studying effective treatments, investigating behaviors, and improving lives in other ways. How we conduct the research involve key ethical considerations.

The following are the ethical considerations on this study:

Protect the rights of research participants, by practicing confidentiality of all the information or answer in the questionnaire or instrument.

Participants should know the purpose, benefits, risks, and funding behind the study before they agree or decline to join.

Participants should be free to opt in or out of the study at any point in time.

Physical, social, psychological and all other types of harm are kept to an absolute minimum.

Participants information must be keep hidden from everyone else. Anonymize personally identifiable data so that it can't be linked to other data by anyone else.

Ensure the study is free of plagiarism or research misconduct and accurately represent the results.

Enhance research validity.

Maintain scientific or academic integrity.

Results and Discussion

This section includes the data gathered from the researcher instrument, computed, interpreted, and analysed.

Profile of the Respondents

Table 1. *Demographic Profile of the Respondent (Teachers and school heads)*

Category	Teacher		School Head	
	F	%	F	%
Sex				
Male	18	18%	6	60%
Female	82	62%	4	40%
Total	100	100 %	10	100%
Age				
18-29	20	20%	0	0
26-35	26	26%	0	0
36-45	31	31%	1	10%
46-55	15	15%	5	50%
55 and above	8	8%	4	40%
Total	100	100 %	10	100%
Length of Service				
1-10	30	30 %	0	0
11-20	26	26 %	0	0
21-30	24	24 %	4	40%
40 and above	20	20 %	6	60%
Total	100	100 %	10	100%
Position				
T1	39	39%	0	0%
T2	31	31%	0	0%
T3	30	30%	0	0%
Principal/School Head			10	100%
Total	100	100 %	10	100%

Table 1 presents the demographic profile of the Respondents. As shown in the table, majority of the teacher respondents were female almost 82 or 82%, while most of the school heads were male or 5 out of 10. As to the ages of the respondents, majority of the teachers were on the aged bracket between 36-45 years, and least in number on above 45 years of aged. On the other hand, majority of the school head were on the aged bracket between 46-55 and above. This indicate that the ages of the respondents were normally distributed.

As to the length of service, majority of the teachers have served the institution for 20 to 30 year comprising of almost 50%. On the other hand, school have longer length of service which is 30 years to above 40years in the service.

With respect to the positions of the respondents, 39 respondents or were Teacher 1; 31 were Teacher 3; were Teacher 2; and 10 were school head

Level of Role of School Heads

The school head themselves indicates their Supervision and monitoring (Feedback) role is to supervise and monitor the work and behaviour of teachers, create an orderly atmosphere in the school and observe instruction in classrooms were practice to a very high extent with rating ranging from 5.00-4.20.

On instructional support the school heads themselves indicates they give teachers suggestions to h improve their teaching; When a teacher has problems in the classroom, they take the initiative to discuss matters and they also take over lessons from teachers who are unexpectedly absent which to them the practice it to a very high extent.

On Teacher's Empowerment, school heads make sure they encourage teacher professional development; Inform them about possibilities for updating their knowledge and skills and give teachers freedom to choose their own instructional techniques were practice by school heads to a very high extent with weighted mean ranging form 5.00 to 4.20.

Table 2. *The role of school heads Towards building Teachers Positive Identity per assessment of the teachers and the school head themselves*

Statement	School head		Teachers	
	WM	D	WM	D
Supervision and Feedback				
1. Supervise and monitor the work and behaviour of teachers	4.82	VHE	4.42	VHE
2. Create an orderly atmosphere in the school.	4.92	VHE	4.76	VHE
3. Observe instruction in classrooms.	4.92	VHE	4.85	VHE
General Weighted Mean	4.88	VHE	4.67	VHE
Instructional Support				
1. Give teachers suggestions as to how they can improve their teaching.	4.71	VHE	4.78	VHE
2. When a teacher has problems in his/her classroom, take the initiative to discuss matters	4.71	VHE	4.68	VHE
3. Take over lessons from teachers who are unexpectedly absent	4.28	VHE	4.02	HE
General Weighted Mean	4.88	VHE	4.56	VHE
Teacher's Empowerment				
1. Make sure that the teacher enhances their professional development.	4.82	VHE	4.80	VHE
2. Inform teachers about possibilities for updating their knowledge and skills	4.84	VHE	4.72	VHE
3. Give teachers freedom to choose their own instructional techniques	4.84	VHE	4.80	VHE
General Weighted Mean	4.83	VHE	4.77	VHE

Legend: 5.00-4.20 Very High extent; 2.59-1.8 Low extent; 4.19- 3.4 High extent; 1.79- 1.00 Very Low extent; 3.39- 2.6 Moderate extent

To the teacher they indicate their school head role on Supervision and Feedback to a very high extent particularly on Observing instruction in classrooms; Supervise and monitor the work and behaviour of teachers and creating an orderly atmosphere in the school. Which obtained weighted mean ranging from 5.00 to 4.20

On Teacher's Empowerment role of school head, teacher rated their school head to have practice these roles to a very high extent particularly on advising teacher to enhance their professional development; Inform teachers about possibilities for updating their knowledge and skills and give them teachers freedom to choose their own instructional techniques which obtained rating ranging between 5.00-- to 4.20

Building Positive Levels of Teacher's Identity

Table 3 presents the respondents (teachers and school heads) perception on building positive levels of teacher's identity. On professional competence, school heads indicate they cultivate leadership in others with weighted mean of 4.74; Improved their school leadership with 4.84 and ensure to improve their subordinate teaching skills with a weighted 4.87. These were always visible and with excellent performance as seen by school heads.

On mastery of the subjects matter, school heads perceived, three items as always evident in their subordinate (teacher) which were describe as Excellence: These were as follows: Ensure that teachers are held accountable for the attainment of the school's goals with weighted mean of 4.71; Resolve problems with the timetable and/or lesson planning with 4.71 and monitor the performance of teachers as well as their teaching duties with 4.28.

Table 3. *Respondents Assessment on Building Positive Levels Of Teacher's Identity*

Statement	School head		Teachers	
	WM	D	WM	D
Professional Competence				
1. Cultivating leadership in others	4.74	E	4.82	E
2. Improving School Leadership	4.84	E	4.92	E
3. Ensure that the teaching skills of the staff are improving	4.87	E	4.92	E
General Weighted Mean	4.82	E	4.88	
Mastery Of The Subjects				
1. Ensure that teachers are held accountable for the attainment of the school's goals	4.71	E	4.28	E
2. Resolve problems with the timetable and/or lesson planning	4.71	E	4.82	E
3. Monitor the performance of teachers as well as their teaching duties	4.28	E	4.71	E
General Weighted Mean	4.82	E	4.60	E
Relationship With Peers				
1. Check for mistakes and errors in administrative procedures and reports for a peaceful organization	4.84	E	4.92	E
2. Involve the teachers in the decision- making processes: sharing power and responsibilities	4.82	E	4.89	E
3. Identify the professional development needs of teachers	4.92	E	4.84	E
General Weighted Mean	4.82	E	4.88	E

Legend: 5.00-4.20 Very High extent; 2.59-1.8 Low extent; 4.19- 3.4 High extent; 1.79- 1.00 Very Low extent; 3.39- 2.6 Moderate extent

On relationship with peers, school heads indicated the need for professional growth of teachers, got the highest weighted mean of 4.92; Checking for mistakes and errors in administrative procedures and reports for a peaceful organization got a weighted mean of 4.84 and the last involving the teachers in the decision-making processes, sharing power and responsibilities obtained weighted mean of 4.82. All three items were practice with excellence.

On the other hand teachers assessment on school heads practices on building positive levels of teacher’s identity particularly on Professional Competence, teachers indicated that school heads ensure that the teaching skills of the staff/subordinate are improving with weighted mean of 4.82; they wanted that teacher will Improved School Leadership with weighted mean of 4.84 and Cultivates leadership in others with weighted mean of 4.74. These items were practice with excellence.

On mastery of the subjects teacher assess their school heads, resolve problems with the timetable and/or lesson planning with a rating of 4.82; monitor the performance of teachers as well as their teaching duties got a weighted mean of 4.71 and the last ensure that teachers are held accountable for the attainment of the school’s goals with weighted mean of 4.28 at descriptively mean as practice with excellence.

Teachers assess their school heads on the relationship with peer to be excellent in their practice with checking for mistakes and errors in administrative procedures and reports for a peaceful organization got weighted mean of 4.92;Involved their teachers in the decision-making processes: sharing power and responsibilities with weighted mean of 4.89 and Identify the professional development needs of teachers with weighted mean of 4.84

Difference on the Assessment of the Teachers and School Heads Themselves onthe Role of School Head

Table 4. *T-test Result on the Significant difference on the assessment of school heads and teacher on the role of School Heads*

Category	Schoolhead	Teachers	T-computed	T-test table value	Decision
Supervision and Feedback.	4.29	4.67	0.0975	3.182	Not significant
Instructional Support	4.36	4.49	0.1871	3.182	Not significant
Teacher’s Empowerment	4.83	4.77	0.0333	3.182	Not significant

Table 4 present the t-test Result on the Significant difference on the assessment of the school heads and teacher on the role of School Heads. As presented in the table, there were no significant difference on the assessment of the school head and teachers on the role of the performance of the school heads on the three category: Supervision and Feedback; Instructional Support and Teacher’s Empower. As shown in the table on Supervision and Feedback the computed t-test value was 0.0975; Instructional Support; with competed value of .18718 and on Teacher’s Empowerment was 0.03338, these values were less that than or table value of t-test at degree of freedom at 5% probability level. Hence the not hypothesis that “there is no significant difference in the assessment of the school head and teachers on the performance of the school heads relative to their role relative to Supervision and Feedback; Instructional Support and Teacher’s Empower. These mean that the two groups have the same assessment on the performance of their school heads on their respective role, relative to the three category.

Difference On The Assessment Of The Teachers And School Heads Themselves relative to building teachers identity

Table 5. *T-test Result on the Significant difference on the assessment of school heads and teacher relative to building teachers identity*

Category	Schoolhead	Teachers	T-computed	T-test table value	Decision
professional competence	4.82	4.88	0.12295	3.182	Not significant
mastery of subjects;	4.82	4.60	0.4374	3.182	Not significant
Relationship with peers	4.82	4.82	0.2883	3.182	Not significant

Table 5 present the t-test Result on the Ssignificant difference on the assessment of school heads and teacher relative to building teachers identity. As shown in the table the computed t-test value of 0.12295 professional competence; 0.4374 mastery of subjects; and 0.2883 for Relationship with peers were less than the table value 3.182 at 3 degree of freedom ans 05% probability level.

This lead to the acceptance of the Null hypothesis that there is no significance difference in the assessment of the school head and the teachers relative to building teachers identity of the school heads. Hence it can be stated that the assessment of the two groups are the same.

Relationship between the role of school heads and positive teachers Identity:

Table 6. *T-test Result on the Significant result of Pearson coefficient correlation on the assessment of school heads role and teacher-building identity*

Positive teachers Identity:	School Heads Role	Pearson r computed	Decision
professional competence	Supervision and Feedback.	4.48	.30 to .50
mastery of subjects;	Instructional Support	4.425	0.452
Relationship with peers	Teacher’s Empowerment	4.80	Low positive correlation

As shown in Table 6 the result of Pearson coefficient correlation the computed r of 0.452 is interpreted as Low positive correlation between the Role of the principal and Building teachers identity. There might other factor that may enhance the relationship.

Since the finding indicate the very high extent on most of the items on the role of school head, all of the items indicated on this study are useful in building the positive identity of the teachers. The role of School Heads particularly on Supervision and Feedback; Instructional Support; Teacher's Empowerment are significant in building the positive Teacher's Identity. These were justified by the different review of literature presented in this study.

Conclusions

Based on the finding of the study the following conclusion were based:

There were more female teachers, middle age and more than 10 years in the service.

On the assessment of the two groups from the school head and the teachers Assessment on the Role of School Heads. The school head themselves indicates their Supervision and monitoring (Feedback); instructional support and Teacher's Empowerment, were practice to a very high extent as assess by themselves on the teachers

To the teacher they indicate their school head role on Supervision and Feedback to a very high extent particularly on observing instruction in classrooms; Supervise and monitor the work and behaviour of teachers and creating an orderly atmosphere in the school. On Teacher's Empowerment role of school head, teacher rated their school head to have practice these roles to a very high extent particularly on advising teacher to enhances their professional development; Inform teachers about possibilities for updating their knowledge and skills and give them teachers freedom to choose their own instructional techniques.

On Building Positive Levels Of Teacher's Identity, the respondents (teachers and school heads) assessment on building positive levels of teacher's identity, and mastery of the subjects matter were always visible and with excellent performance as seen by school heads.

On relationship with peers, school heads indicated were practice with excellence.

On the other hand teachers assessment on school heads practices on building positive levels of teacher's identity and mastery of the subjects particularly on Professional Competence, were practice with excellence. On the relationship with peer was excellent in their practice

All of the items indicated on this study and are useful in building the positive identity of the teachers

Based on the finding and conclusion the following were recommendations:

The finding of this study indicated the importance of a school head in building the school environment. Thus in context of the school as it relates to the roles, dispositions, and perceptions of teacher identity is worthy of further investigation. School head must recognize area to tap leadership sources critical to school improvement efforts. Further research into this distinction may add to the school reform.

Teacher identity in this study defined themselves through their interactions with other members of the school communities in which they worked these teachers described what it means to be who they are in terms of an educational role model, decision maker, a visionary, a positional designer, The behaviors that they demonstrated through their descriptions of the work in which they engaged and their relationships with the principal or other teachers were shaped by the school structure. Thus proper engagement with their school head will best build their identity. Further study on this concept should be done.

Examination of the differences in the ability to lead, the desire to lead, and the opportunity to lead may further clarify the formal and informal nature of school head. Further study is recommended to future research in this area.

Viewing school heads leadership through the lens of those at the school level provides direction for school improvement efforts by illuminating the successes and barriers that teachers face as they strive to work beyond the classroom. This study is recommend to widen the level of understanding of this component of school reform at all levels. A further study on this concept is recommended.

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